

Regain Consciousness: The Impact of Internet Pornography on Children And Adolescents – A Review

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ABSTRACT: Excessive pornography consumption may distort children's and adolescent's perceptions of relationships, intimacy, and body image, fostering unrealistic expectations that contribute to confusion and dissatisfaction. The normalization of such content can also lead to the reinforcement of gender stereotypes and unhealthy views on sex, which may have long-term psychological consequences. This systematic literature review aimed to identify the impact of internet pornography on children and adolescents. The review attained and identified four themes: Showing Emotional and Behavioral Issues, Lacking Parental Engagement in Digital Literacy and Online Safety for Children and Adolescents, Promoting Unhealthy Sexual Behaviors due to Excessive Porn Consumption, and Addressing the Psychological and Developmental Effects of Internet Pornography. Teaching internet literacy and safe online behaviors in schools is critical, as it prepares learners to navigate the digital world responsibly, identify unsafe content, and make educated media consumption decisions. Encouraging participation in extracurricular activities is also healthier as it fosters friendships, teamwork, and a feeling of purpose. When young people are included and valued within an environment, they are less likely to seek approval from pornography, lowering their dependency on explicit content and improving their emotional well-being.

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INTRODUCTION

For children and adolescents who frequently use the internet and social media, one of the negative effects of technological progress is the availability of pornography. The easy access to and dependence on the media as a means of establishing intimate relationships with others and exposing them to pornographic material is the first factor contributing to the rise in pornographic consumption habits in every generation (Astuti & Winarti, 2022).

Globally, a cross-sectional online survey of Australians aged 15 to 29 revealed that 87% of them had viewed porn at some point, with the median age at first viewing being 13 years for men and 16 years for women. An Italian study of 1492 students in their senior year of high school found that 78% of internet users watched porn, and of these, 8% watched it daily, 59% thought it was always stimulating, 22% described it as habitual, 10% said it decreased sexual interest in potential real-life partners, and 9% reported a form of addiction. More frequent viewing was associated with male gender, non-heterosexual identity, higher education, younger age, and recent mental health problems (Kirby, 2021).

In 2021, Pornhub, a well-known international porn website, said that the Philippines ranked first in the globe for the longest duration of time spent watching pornographic films in a single visit (Garcia, 2021). Hence, this could mean that frequent watching of the said may significantly impact viewers with the possible negative outcomes of watching the content videos.

Moreover, the study is grounded in Bandura's (1977) social learning theory, which focuses on social learning as discovering and imitating particular actions through media content. This includes sexually explicit content, which may be sampled and usually highlights relevant actions. Teens who are exposed to pornography will ultimately get thrilled after seeing, recording, and mimicking it. Pornographic content satisfaction serves as the foundation for the defense of sexual behaviors via oppression and violence.

In addition, the Social Script Theory discusses how individuals follow internal social interaction scripts that provide direction and purpose (Gagnon & Simon, 1973; Simon & Gagnon, 1986). Another way to think of scripts is as normative references that specify guidelines for action lines in certain social circumstances. (Libby & Gecas, 1976). Scripts are acquired through mass media consumption and direct observation of others.

However, there is a significant lack of research on specific challenges we face locally, including the rising problem of porn addiction among teenagers. This issue has not been adequately addressed despite its prevalence, leaving us without the necessary information to understand its impact on our youth and the community. Teenagers are often exposed to explicit content early on, leading to unhealthy perceptions of relationships and various mental health issues. Without localized studies, we struggle to identify what our community needs to address this issue effectively. Focused research is essential to tackle these problems. Filling this gap will help us develop solutions and strategies that truly support our youth and promote healthier development within our community.

This study supports Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 3 – Good Health and Well-being of the United Nations, which aims to ensure everyone's health and well-being by acknowledging that exposure to pornography, particularly throughout early life, can have negative mental health effects like anxiety, a distorted body image, and harmful perspectives on relationships and sexuality. Additionally, the study is also addressed in SDG 5 – Gender Equality, which aims to promote gender equality, and some types of pornography can legitimize violence, objectify individuals, and reinforce negative gender stereotypes, all of which can affect how people view gender roles and relationships.

METHOD

Research Design

A systematic literature review (SLR), a qualitative approach, was used in this study to examine the problem of exposure to pornography and its effects on children and adolescents. A systematic literature review is a deliberate and accurate approach to finding, assessing, and summarizing prior research relevant to a topic or investigation. A detailed search is conducted across several databases, academic journals, literature, and other resources to locate all relevant studies on the subject. The criteria should be effectively defined prior to the investigation, and the plan or technique of the systematic review should be established. This systematic and open search can be rewritten by multiple researchers utilizing a variety of databases and sources from the grey literature. This entails organizing a comprehensive search strategy and placing a strong emphasis on responding to a recognized question (Dewey & Drahota, 2016).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results drawn from the selected papers, the following statements and credible information should be emphasized in this paper, as shown in Table 1.

This review attained and identified four themes about raising awareness regarding early exposure to pornography: *Showing Emotional and Behavioral Issues, Lacking Parental Engagement in Digital Literacy and Online Safety for Children and Adolescents, Promoting Unhealthy Sexual Behaviors due to Excessive Porn Consumption, and Addressing the Psychological and Developmental Effects of Internet Pornography*. Many teenagers often browse the internet without much caution, which could result in unintended exposure to pornographic content. This exposure may lead to emotional challenges that affect their behavior, shaping their perceptions of relationships, sex, and body image and causing unrealistic expectations or confusion about intimacy. Pornography exposure can promote unhealthy sexual behaviors among children and adolescents by normalizing unrealistic standards and behaviors that may not reflect real-life relationships. The situation is further complicated by limited parental involvement in discussions about digital literacy and online safety, as many parents may be unaware or unsure of how to address the risks associated with their children's exposure to explicit material.

Showing Emotional and Behavioral Issues

The first theme generated during the data gathering is *Showing Emotional and Behavioral Issues*. This indicates that the usage of pornography on the internet by kids and teenagers appears to be linked to various emotional and behavioral problems. Increased anxiety, stress, addiction, isolation, distorted beliefs and perceptions, negative feelings about themselves, and neglecting other areas of their lives are some of the instances in which these problems can show up. This generally means that those who consume internet porn may also act impulsively and irresponsibly. It also suggests that excessive usage of pornography may disrupt normal emotional development, making it harder for them to build positive relationships with others.

Furthermore, Setyawati, Hartini, and Suryanto (2020) supported the theme with the findings that demonstrate complicated themes regarding gender, power, sexual health, body, pleasure, consent, sexuality, and sex are present in graphic material. Repeated

exposure to pornography causes a warped perception of "acceptable" behavior in relationships and has been linked to a decrease in adolescents' sensitivity to the content being seen. The effects of the learning process through imitation will eventually cause inappropriate behavior among adolescents (Genelza, 2022), and pornographic displays will have an eventual harmful influence on changes in attitudes or behavior.

In addition, this was supported by Gasso and Brunch-Granados (2021), expressing that the use of pornography by children and teenagers is one of the most concerning problems resulting from this new online environment. The findings show that early, deliberate exposure to pornographic material could result in a harmful behavioral impact on young people by encouraging sexual addiction and supporting the persistence of gender inequality in tendencies of emotional and sexual interactions.

Anent to the theme presented in this study, it clearly emphasizes the serious consequences that online pornography use can have on children and teenagers. The findings imply that early exposure to explicit content can lead to emotional and behavioral problems such as mood swings, skewed views, and negative self-esteem. These problems can impact general psychological well-being, social interactions, and the development of relationships. It emphasizes the necessity of knowing how early exposure affects young people's mental health and societal behavior. It also highlights the importance of preventive measures, like parental supervision and mental health support, in overcoming potentially harmful consequences. By addressing these issues, we can improve the well-being of children and adolescents in an increasingly digital society.

Lacking Parental Engagement in Digital Literacy and Online Safety for Children and Adolescents

The second theme generated during the data gathering is *Lacking Parental Engagement in Digital Literacy and Online Safety for Children and Adolescents*. This means that children who lack proper guidance from parents unaware of the risks associated with online content are more vulnerable to exposure to inappropriate material. Teenagers who often browse the internet may encounter pornographic material without intending to. As the internet is more accessible at this time, young people can easily stumble upon explicit content through social media and websites. Moreover, early and repeated exposure to such content can have long-term effects on their emotional and psychological development, as they may struggle to distinguish between fantasy and reality in their understanding of healthy sexual relationships.

Besides, this was supported by Liu, Chang, Chiu, Li, Chen, Chen, Lin, and Chiang (2021), who found that there was significant parent-child difference in reports of children being exposed to pornography and violence on mobile devices. Parents were unaware of the violence and pornography their kids are exposed to. Factors like children owning a smartphone and how much time they spend on tablets and smartphones were linked to a lack of parental knowledge of the exposure to pornography on mobile devices.

In addition, Meilani, Hariadi, and Haryadi (2023) stated that the majority of teenagers in Indonesia who had a smartphone and used social media had access to explicit material such as short videos and movies through widely used platforms such as YouTube, Instagram, and WhatsApp. With these platforms being so widely used, it is easy for young individuals to come across inappropriate material, even without actively looking for it. Hence, it is a must to be vigilant (Genelza, 2024).

Hence, the lack of parental involvement in monitoring children's internet use makes them more likely to come across inappropriate content. This exposure may have long-term effects on their development and understanding of relationships. Given how easily accessible explicit information is on popular platforms and how often parents are unaware of their children's internet time, there is a need for improved digital literacy education. Parents and children should talk openly about internet safety and potential risks to help guarantee a safer online experience.

Promoting Unhealthy Sexual Behaviors due to Excessive Porn Consumption

The third theme generated during the data gathering is *Promoting Unhealthy Sexual Behaviors due to Excessive Porn Consumption*. This shows that excessive porn consumption can alter a person's behavior and with even worse effects on adolescents. Since adolescents are in a crucial stage of development, repeated exposure to pornography can change their understanding and view of sex and gender roles in unhealthy ways. In some instances, Adolescents tend to be more gender stereotypical upon excessive porn consumption. This means that those who watch porn a lot can become more aggressive and offensive due to the stereotypical mindset they get from watching porn.

Furthermore, this was supported by Leon, Quiñonez-Toral, and Aizpurura (2025), who stated that excessive pornography consumption is strongly linked to unhealthy sexual behaviors, particularly the normalization of violent sexual practices. Excessive porn usage not only influences how adolescents view sex but it also encourages behaviors that can be harmful in real-life relationships.

Additionally, Pathmendra, Raggatt, Lim, Marino, and Skinner (2023) stated that adolescents who watch porn are more likely to engage in risky and unhealthy sexual practices. Teenagers who watch porn are more likely to have multiple partners, have sex earlier in life, engage in unprotected sex, and even experience or commit acts of sexual aggression. Pornography may influence teenage sexual norms, which could result in negative behaviors at a critical stage of development.

With this, the theme shows the impact of excessive pornography consumption. This concludes that consuming excessive amounts of pornography is linked with risky and unhealthy sexual behavior, particularly in teenagers. Regular exposure to porn is closely associated with aggressive behavior in real-life relationships, the normalization of violent sexual practices, and normalizing gender stereotypes. Furthermore, harmful behaviors such as multiple partners, unprotected sex, and sexual violence contribute to online porn overconsumption by changing people's behavior toward sex and relationships.

Addressing the Psychological and Developmental Effects of Internet Pornography

The fourth theme generated during the data gathering is *Addressing the Psychological and Developmental Effects of Internet Pornography*. This can be interpreted that the internet serves as a shared space where children and teenagers may encounter pornography, whether accidentally or intentionally. Given the widespread accessibility of online content, exposure can occur through various platforms, including social media, advertisements, or peer sharing. This raises concerns about the potential impact on adolescent psychological development, shaping their perceptions of relationships, sexuality, and self-identity. Understanding these effects is crucial for developing effective education, media literacy programs, and parental guidance strategies to foster a healthier digital environment for young people.

Moreover, this was supported by Paulus, Nouri, Ohmann, Möhler, and Popow (2024), who stated that concerns regarding the effects of sexually explicit media on children's and adolescents' attitudes and behavior have grown as a result of their increased access to. Teenagers' views, understanding, and conduct have been impacted and altered by the widespread availability of sexual content, including pornography, made possible by internet-enabled gadgets. According to the study, the amount of young people who purposefully or unintentionally come across pornographic content online has increased dramatically, and the Internet is thought to be a more sexualized environment than traditional forms of media. Early exposure to pornography has a complicated and delicate effect on sexual health, making it a significant public health concern.

Likewise, Fernandez, Kuss, and Griffiths (2021) stated that addiction is a chronic brain disease that affects the circuits responsible for reward, motivation, and memory. This condition leads individuals to seek relief or gratification through substances or behaviors compulsively.

To put it simply, the theme presented in this paper discussed how frequent exposure to online pornography can affect a person's psychological and developmental development, particularly in younger people. It may prevent young people from developing healthy emotional and sexual abilities, including communication. Frequent use can also cause desensitization, which can alter the dynamics of relationships and lower fulfillment in real-life sexual interactions. Regular usage can affect mental health and developmental progress in ways that might not promote healthy, real-world relationships.

Table 1: List of Literature on Internet Pornography

AUTHORS	TITLE OF THE STUDY	LOCALE	METHOD	RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	RECOMMENDATIONS	THEMES
Elisabeth K. Andrie, Irene Ikbale Sakou, Eleni C. Tzavela, Clive Richardson, and Artemis K. Tsitsika (2021)	Adolescents' Online Pornography Exposure and Its Relationship to Sociodemographic and Psychopathological Correlates: A Cross-Sectional Study in Six European Countries	Greece, Spain, Poland, Romania, Netherlands, and Iceland	Quantitative	According to the study's findings, with one in four European teenagers regularly exposed to online pornographic content and comparatively low differences in rates across participating nations, this study demonstrated that exposure to pornography is normal for today's adolescents. Additionally, adolescents who report being exposed to pornography are more likely to exhibit emotional and behavioral issues.	Adolescents' exposure to online pornography may lead to misleading ideas about sex. These problems must be addressed in sex education classes in order to prevent these harmful and distorted views towards sex.	Showing Emotional and Behavioral Issues
Rr. Setyawati, Nurul Hartini, and Suryanto Suryanto (2020)	The Psychological Impacts of Internet Pornography Addiction on Adolescents	Indonesia	Qualitative	The findings demonstrate that complicated themes regarding gender, power, sexual health, body, pleasure, consent, sexuality, and sex are present in graphic material. Repeated exposure to pornography causes a warped perception of "acceptable" behavior in relationships and has been linked to a decrease in adolescents' sensitivity to the content being seen. The effects of the learning process through imitation will eventually	This study recommended the need to acquire internet pornography literacy to protect themselves from exposure to the internet with pornographic content that is increasingly circulating without boundaries. More research is recommended to examine related variables like self-worth, self-image, and social relations of individuals that require handling from several parties, namely the government, parents, and the community.	

				cause inappropriate behavior among adolescents, and pornographic displays will have an eventual harmful influence on changes in attitudes or behavior.	
Darry Mead (2016).	The Risks Young People Face as Porn Consumers	Istanbul, Turkey	Qualitative	Given that youths are becoming major users of internet pornography, it has not been demonstrated to be a safe product from the perspective of risk management, according to the study's findings. It is unsafe, just like any activity, and has a significant risk of harm.	This demands a thorough educational curriculum that begins in elementary and continues through high school. Young people can be encouraged to take on greater responsibility by teaching them about the brain's reward system and how open it is to addiction for their behavior. Pornography as a sex manual can be replaced, or at least lessened, by teaching sexual education that prioritizes respect, consent, and safe physical contact.
Aina M. Gasso and Anna Bruch-Granados (2021)	Psychological and Forensic Challenges Regarding Youth Consumption of Pornography: A Narrative Review	Barcelona, Spain	Qualitative	The use of pornography by children and teenagers is one of the most concerning problems resulting from this new online environment. The findings show that early, deliberate exposure to pornographic material could result in a harmful behavioral impact on young people by encouraging hypersexualization and supporting the persistence of gender inequality in tendencies of	Future study directions should evaluate the actual, immediate, and long-term effects of the problems and difficulties raised. Furthermore, it recommends developing preventive, detection, and intervention strategies for at-risk populations.

				emotional and sexual interactions.	
Eka Apriani (2017)	The Misuse of ICT by Student: The Effects of Pornography and The Teacher Solutions	Indonesia	Qualitative	The study's conclusions show that ICT stands for information and communication technology. People's most commonly used technologies are computers and the internet. The Internet plays a significant part in our lives. The internet has two influences on students: positive and negative. One of the bad consequences of utilizing the internet is pornography. Pornography is extremely dangerous for pupils since it can lower their morality and destroy their bodies, minds, and hearts.	The author makes a recommendation for educators in Indonesia, particularly in South Sumatera, who should protect their students from harmful influences such as pornography along with sharing knowledge. A good strategy to stop pornography in schools is sex education. In addition, Students should receive useful information about sex through sex education. This helps students understand what they should and should not do regarding gender.
Elizabeth Baker (2015)	Online pornography – Should schools be teaching young people about the risks? An exploration of the views of young people and teaching professionals	London, UK	Quantitative	Research findings state that the Internet has increased access to sexually explicit media among young people. Online pornography is diversified, can be graphic, and a huge amount is available for free without any restrictions. Young people's access to online pornography, whether intentional or unintentional, raises concerns about their sexual development and relationships. It also states that research on how	This study suggests that schools should begin educating students about the potential effects of pornography consumption in primary school and continue through secondary school to address various related issues. These issues include safer sex practices, body image and self-esteem, behavior, and attitudes toward the opposite sex, respect, and empowerment.

				pornography affects young people's attitudes and behaviors is inconsistent.		
Angela Davis, Cassandra Wright, Michael Curtis, Margaret Hellard, Megan Lim, and Meredith Temple-Smith (2021)	Not my child': parenting, pornography, and views on education	Melbourne , Australia	Qualitative	Research indicates that sex education and pornographic material are delicate subjects, and further study is required to analyze how parents view this extremely complicated problem to inform social policy and education that is grounded in evidence. The majority of youth will encounter online pornography initially in early childhood or adolescence, which leads to concerns regarding the negative impact of pornography on the sexual attitudes of young viewers.	According to the study, most parents would recommend having an open discussion with their kids about their online behavior rather than depending on rules or filters at home. This emphasizes how crucial it is that we help parents by encouraging communication and offering tools for teaching kids about digital literacy and internet safety.	Lacking Parental Engagement in Digital Literacy and Online Safety for Children and Adolescents
Angela C Davis, Cassandra JC Wright, Stacey Murphy, Paul Dietze, Meredith J Temple-Smith, Margaret E Hellard, Megan SC Lim. (2020).	A Digital Pornography Literacy Resource Co-Designed with Vulnerable Young People: Development of "The Gist"	Melbourne , Australia	Qualitative	The study concluded that while the participants were able to identify problems with pornography and assess its content, they lacked the information necessary to understand alternative healthy attitudes and actions. This lack of knowledge prevented them from fully exploring and embracing healthier perspectives on sexuality and relationships.	In order to improve engagement with these resources and make the content more impactful and relevant, the study suggested incorporating insights into pornography literacy messages to address underlying attitudes. This could be achieved by analyzing user interaction patterns from popular digital platforms and understanding information-seeking behaviors.	

<p>Luis Brage Ballester, Carmen Orte Socias, and Carlos Varela Rosón (2022)</p>	<p>A survey study on pornography consumption among young Spaniards and its impact on interpersonal relationships</p>	<p>Spain</p>	<p>Quantitative</p>	<p>Based on the data acquired, introduction to pornography can occur when a person is at an early age (eight years old). Both pornography and the Internet are alternatives to effective sexual education, evidently affecting teenagers' and children's views and attitudes and raising risky actions. This condition, along with a lack of approaches to tackle sexual education challenges, could be a problematic factor in terms of developing healthy sexual relationships.</p>	<p>It is recommended that effective sexual education should be improved, and the role of various socialization agents should be monitored. The ever-younger introduction and familiarity with new technology are factors that must be studied further, considering that the majority of pornography consumption methods are from using computers and mobile phones.</p>
<p>Jessica D. Zurcher (2017)</p>	<p>Exploring descriptive norms of parent-child communication about pornography among parents of middle-schoolers in the US</p>	<p>USA</p>	<p>Qualitative</p>	<p>The study's presented viewpoints imply that the majority of parents view teens' exposure to pornography as harmful, and despite exposure, sexually explicit material has been growing more common among youths. Challenges such as parental fear, discomfort, and a lack of sexual openness and knowledge about technological communication were delivered.</p>	<p>Open, frequent, and direct discussion regarding pornography is necessary. Parents are encouraged to increase parental education about adult content and promote the value of overall healthy relationships between parents and their children.</p>
<p>Shumei Liu, Fong-Ching Chang, Chiung-Hui Chiu, Fubao Li, Ping-</p>	<p>Parent-Child Discrepancies in Reports of Exposure to Violence/Pornography on Mobile</p>	<p>Taiwan & China</p>	<p>Quantitative</p>	<p>This study assessed how reports from parents and children differed about the exposure of young people to the impact of pornography and</p>	<p>Parents are strongly advised to communicate openly and consistently with their children regarding their digital activities to improve</p>

<p>Hung Chen, Chen-Yu Chen, Yi-Pin Lin, and Jeng-Tung Chiang (2021)</p>	<p>Devices and the Impact on Children's Psychosocial Adjustment</p>			<p>violence on mobile devices on children's mental development. The findings showed that 80% of the respondents were unaware of this. It also demonstrates how exposure to this content causes behavioral and emotional issues in children and adolescents.</p>	<p>their understanding of the online threats their children experience. Parents may better understand the possible risks by establishing an environment where kids feel free to talk about their online experiences.</p>
<p>Damiano Pizzol, Alessandro Bertoldo and Carlo Foresta (2015)</p>	<p>Adolescents and web porn: a new era of sexuality</p>	<p>Italy</p>	<p>Quantitative</p>	<p>The survey among 1492 individuals revealed that all have access to the Internet, and the majority (1283, 86%) access the Web regularly. Only 45 (3%) reported they accessed the web less than once a week, while the remaining 11% stated they did not access it daily but did more than once per week. In addition, the study findings indicate that pornography can affect the lifestyles of adolescents, especially in terms of their sexual habits and porn consumption. They may have a significant influence on their sexual attitudes and behaviors.</p>	<p>There is a need to study and manage online content, mostly due to its easy access, the health concerns on certain websites, and the uncontrolled usage of pornography. It is important to educate internet users, particularly children and teens, about the safe and ethical use of the Internet and its contents. Furthermore, public education campaigns should be improved in quality and frequency to help improve knowledge of sexual behavior issues on the Internet raised by both adolescents and parents.</p>
<p>Wiwi Yunengsih and Agus Setiawan (2022)</p>	<p>Contribution of Pornographic Exposure and Addiction to Risky Sexual Behavior in</p>	<p>Indonesia</p>	<p>Quantitative</p>	<p>The study discovered that adolescents' risky sexual practices are greatly increased by early exposure to pornography and</p>	<p>The study highlights the vital need for preventative measures, parental monitoring, and improved sexual education in order to</p>

	Adolescents			higher levels of addiction. Early sexual activity, several partners, and hazardous sex were more common among individuals who were exposed at a younger age and who regularly watched pornographic videos. According to the findings, pornography reinforces curiosity-driven watching that can lead to addiction by influencing sexual norms and practices.	lessen the dangers of young exposure to pornography and risky sexual activity. Additionally, it emphasizes the importance of promoting open communication between parents and young people.
Niken Meilani, Sunarru Samsi Hariadi, and Fransiskus Trisakti Haryadi (2023)	Social Media and Pornography Access Behavior Among Adolescents	Yogyakarta, Indonesia	Quantitative	Research indicates that most Indonesians born with internet and computer literacy were among Generation Z. Social media and the internet held significance. According to the results, all respondents had smartphones and used social media, with YouTube, Instagram, and WhatsApp being the most widely used platforms, leading to most of them having access to explicit material such as short videos and movies.	It is recommended to control access to internet pornography, which serves as a gateway for sexually risky actions. Adolescents at a vulnerable age require further information and guidance from their families, schools, and communities regarding their use of smartphones and social media.

<p>Rebecca Nufer (2017)</p>	<p>Pornography and its Effects on Physical, Psychological, and Emotional Health in Youth</p>	<p>USA</p>	<p>Qualitative</p>	<p>According to the study, pornography has been more common for several decades, and its impacts are becoming more noticeable every day as a result of its accessibility, cost, and lack of accountability. People of all ages, particularly kids and teenagers, can now access it more easily, unaware of the harm it may cause.</p>	<p>The study advises better prevent the individual from experiencing the problem in the first place. To stop the spread of pornography exposure in kids and teens, society ought to alter its viewpoint on pornography and its consequences, and parents need to be more active in their kids' online activity.</p>	<p>Promoting Unhealthy Sexual Behaviors due to Excessive Porn Consumption</p>
<p>Jochen Peter and Patti M. Valkenburg (2016)</p>	<p>Adolescents and Pornography: A Review of 20 Years of Research</p>	<p>Netherlands</p>	<p>Qualitative</p>	<p>Research indicates that pornography use among teenagers varies greatly, but it is more common among males, sensation-seekers, and those with weaker familial ties. Stronger gender stereotypes, more permissive sexual attitudes, and casual sexual behaviors are all associated with frequent exposure to such content. The study emphasizes the necessity for a more thorough investigation to elucidate these relationships.</p>	<p>In schools and colleges, the research findings should promote sex education as it is one way to at least lessen the impact of pornography. Sex education must be incorporated into the curriculum immediately to prevent the formation of false ideas about sexuality in teenagers. Any exposure to pornographic material should be viewed as a health risk to teenagers, and interventions should be put in place to increase parental supervision of their children's exposure to pornographic media.</p>	

<p>Pranujan Pathmendra, Michelle Raggatt, Megan SC Lim, Jennifer L Marino, and S Rachel Skinner (2023)</p>	<p>Exposure to Pornography and Adolescent Sexual Behavior: Systematic Review</p>	<p>Australia</p>	<p>Qualitative</p>	<p>According to the study, seeing violent adolescent pornography makes people more tolerant of risky behavior and sexual violence. This demonstrates how harmful sexual standards and practices are shaped by pornography consumption.</p>	<p>The study recommends implementing comprehensive sex education that addresses media influence, promoting parental guidance and open discussions, and enforcing stricter regulations on violent pornographic content. It also suggests providing mental health support for adolescents affected by compulsive use and exposure to harmful sexual norms.</p>
<p>Hamdija Begovic (2017)</p>	<p>Pornography Induced Erectile Dysfunction Among Young Men</p>	<p>Sweden</p>	<p>Qualitative</p>	<p>The study looks at pornography-induced erectile dysfunction (PIED), a condition in which men who consume too much online pornography have problems with their sexual potency. The study, which used online diaries and qualitative interviews, posits a causal relationship between erectile dysfunction and extended usage of pornography, which frequently begins in youth. Users eventually need more intense content to stay aroused, which makes in-person sex boring and causes erection problems, which may result in harmful outcomes.</p>	<p>Professionals are encouraged to take into account a patient's amount of pornography viewing and warn them about the possible health consequences while treating conditions like erectile dysfunction. Moreover, more research is required to determine the effects of prolonged exposure to pornography on sexual health, particularly longitudinal studies.</p>

<p>Frank W. Paulus, Foujan Nouri, Susanne Ohmann, Eva Möhler, and Christian Popow (2024)</p>	<p>The Impact of Internet Pornography on Children and Adolescents: A Systematic Review</p>	<p>Homburg/Saar, Germany</p>	<p>Quantitative</p>	<p>The study found that pornography consumption is linked to personal traits, attitudes, and behaviors. With the Internet's accessibility, societal views have shifted from moral condemnation to social acceptance. Online pornography use is influenced by external factors like peers, family, and society, as well as personal traits such as risk-taking and thrill-seeking.</p>	<p>Since its impact on children's development is still uncertain, the study recommended further research better to understand the potential risks and inclusive sexual health education for everyone to be informed and lessen potential harm.</p>	<p>Addressing the Psychological and Developmental Effects of Internet Pornography</p>
<p>Aleksandar Štulhofer, Azra Tafro & Taylor Kohut (2019)</p>	<p>The dynamics of adolescents' pornography use and psychological well-being: a six-wave latent growth and latent class modeling approach</p>	<p>Europe, Croatia</p>	<p>Quantitative</p>	<p>Results show that there were clear gender differences in how often people used pornography, as well as in their levels of depression, anxiety, and self-esteem. Compared to females, males used pornography more often and had higher self-esteem, but they also had lower levels of depression and anxiety. On the other hand, for adolescent females, using pornography more often was linked to higher levels of anxiety and depression.</p>	<p>It is recommended that schools should introduce media literacy programs that emphasize critical conversations about sexualized media, including pornography. In order to encourage healthy attitudes and media awareness, comprehensive sexuality education should address the possible effects of pornography, especially for female teenagers in earlier developmental stages.</p>	

<p>Josep M. Farré ,Angel L. Montejo , Miquel Agulló ,Roser Granero, Carlos Chiclana Actis, Alejandro Villena, Eudald Maideu, Marta Sánchez ,Fernando Fernández-Aranda, Susana (2020)</p>	<p>Pornography Use in Adolescents and Its Clinical Implications</p>	<p>Barcelona, Spain, Salamanca, Spain, Madrid, Spain</p>	<p>Quantitative</p>	<p>The study examined whether social, developmental, and dispositional factors predict pornography use and whether they also influence its relationship with other behavioral factors. One key dispositional factor considered was sexual orientation. A small portion of participants did not specify their sexual orientation, while a slightly larger group identified as lesbian, gay, or bisexual.</p>	<p>According to the study, there is a need to evaluate pornography use in clinical assessments that can help determine its impact on psychosexual development, sexual lifestyle, quality of life, and risk behaviors. Early detection is crucial, as problematic use may be linked to mental health issues, and understanding these factors can help distinguish between normal and problematic use, ultimately preventing hypersexuality and sexual dysfunction in adulthood.</p>
<p>Himani Adarsh and Swapnajeet Sahoo (2023)</p>	<p>Pornography and its impact on adolescent/teenage Sexuality</p>	<p>India</p>	<p>Qualitative</p>	<p>The study highlights concern about teenagers' exposure to pornography due to potential developmental risks. Researchers have explored its impact on cognitive, behavioral, and emotional responses, noting that adolescence involves sexual maturation, including bodily changes, hormones, fantasies, and attraction.</p>	<p>Research is needed to develop and assess theoretical models that explain behavioral patterns and traits linked to adolescent pornography use. Such studies can provide valuable insights into its psychological, emotional, and social effects by identifying associated phenotypes.</p>

The study highlights the impact of early exposure to internet pornography on children and adolescents, highlighting four major themes as stated in the literature mentioned above: emotional and behavioral issues, lack of parental engagement in digital literacy, promotion of unhealthy sexual behaviors, and psychological developmental effects. Many teenagers browse the internet without caution, often leading to unintended exposure to explicit content. This exposure can result in emotional challenges, such as anxiety, stress, mood swings, isolation, and impulsive behaviors (Genelza, 2022).

Additionally, excessive pornography consumption may distort young people's perceptions of relationships, intimacy, and body image, fostering unrealistic expectations that contribute to confusion and dissatisfaction. The normalization of such content can also lead to the reinforcement of gender stereotypes and unhealthy views on sex, which may have long-term psychological

consequences. Furthermore, studies suggest that exposure to pornography at a young age can negatively influence self-esteem, making adolescents more vulnerable to risky behaviors and emotional instability. These effects highlight the necessity of understanding the broader implications of early exposure to explicit material, particularly in an era where internet access is more prevalent than ever.

Another critical aspect explored in the study is the lack of parental engagement in digital literacy and online safety. Many parents remain unaware of the explicit content their children may encounter online, leading to a significant gap in guidance and protection. Research shows that adolescents who own smartphones, laptops, and computers and frequently use social media are more likely to be exposed to pornography, often without their parents' knowledge. This lack of awareness can make it difficult for young individuals to distinguish between reality and fantasy when it comes to healthy relationships and sexuality.

Excessive pornography consumption has also been strongly linked to unhealthy sexual behaviors, including increased aggression, normalization of violent sexual practices, and engagement in risky sexual activities such as unprotected sex and multiple partnerships. As such, the study underscores the need for parental supervision, open discussions about online safety, and digital literacy programs to address these concerns. By implementing these preventive measures, society can help safeguard children and adolescents from the potentially harmful effects of pornography exposure, ensuring their psychological and emotional well-being in an increasingly digital world.

CONCLUSION

With all the data gathered and papers reviewed, it is known that the consumption of pornography has detrimental effects on adolescents. Porn has been more accessible than ever; its influence has grown, shaping how adolescents perceive sex, relationships, and even themselves. What was once considered an issue affecting only a small population has become a broad societal concern. Porn affects millions worldwide, and most of them are adolescents. Adolescents are more vulnerable since their brains are still developing; they are more prone to compulsive behavior and may struggle to regulate their consumption.

Additionally, porn has different impacts on adolescents; it can be psychological, physiological, or emotional aspects. Psychologically, excessive porn consumption can rewire the brain's reward system, which can lead to addiction, where they feel the need to watch more, often seeking more extreme content. This can also be the cause of anxiety and depression. Physiologically, too much porn consumption can interfere with normal sexual development. Some adolescents may develop unrealistic expectations about sex, leading to difficulties with intimacy later in life. Emotionally, constant exposure to pornography can change their views about sex in general. Since much of mainstream porn prioritizes physical gratification over emotional connection, adolescents who watch it excessively may start to see sex as purely transactional rather than a meaningful act built on trust and respect.

Thus, excessive pornography consumption can have lasting effects on adolescents and children, shaping their perceptions of sex, relationships, and intimacy in unhealthy ways. As they become more exposed to unrealistic and often aggressive portrayals of sex, they may develop distorted expectations that can affect their real-life interactions. Over time, this can lead to difficulties in making meaningful relationships. With porn being more accessible than ever, it is important to know its impact on adolescents and spread awareness about this.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the study, one of the positive ways to control sexually explicit media's effects on children is through open family communication, which develops a trusting environment in which kids feel comfortable addressing sensitive topics such as sex and media consumption. Transparency between parents and children is essential because it allows young people to ask questions, express concerns, and obtain factual information instead of seeking answers from potentially risky online sources. By accomplishing open communication between parents, families can create a safer environment for children by helping them build a responsible and informed perspective on sexuality and relationships.

Sexual education programs in schools should include information about same-sex sexuality in order to provide students with accurate and inclusive understanding while minimizing their reliance on pornography as a source of information. Many young individuals come upon pornographic material, frequently using it to fill gaps in their understanding of sex and relationships. Pornography, on the other hand, portrays intimacy, consent, and sexual health in unrealistic and misleading ways, which can influence negative attitudes and expectations. By including same-sex sexuality in the curriculum, schools may ensure that students obtain accurate and reliable information on various sexual orientations, relationships, and safe behaviors. Furthermore, teaching internet literacy and safe online behaviors in schools is critical, as it prepares learners to navigate the digital world responsibly, identify unsafe content, and make educated media consumption decisions.

Finally, encouraging healthy interests and extracurricular activities such as sports, arts, music, and volunteering to keep young people involved in positive and meaningful experiences. When Children and Adolescents lack significant connections with others, they may turn to internet pornography to cope with loneliness or unfulfilled emotional needs. Encouraging participation in extracurricular activities is a healthier way to meet this desire because it fosters friendships, teamwork, and a feeling of purpose. When young people are included and valued within an environment, they are less likely to seek approval from pornography, lowering their dependency on explicit content and improving their emotional well-being.

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